

STRATEGIC ANALYSIS OF THE PROSPECTS OF UZBEKISTAN'S FOREIGN TRADE RELATIONS.

Bekchanov Davron Alisher ugli

(Advisor to the Director for Foreign Economic Affairs of the publishing and printing house "Uzbekistan") (feaiptduzbekistan@gmail.com)

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Annotation. Uzbekistan, a landlocked country in Central Asia, has been increasingly active in enhancing its foreign trade relations since gaining independence from the Soviet Union in 1991. The nation's strategic location, abundant natural resources, and ambitious economic reforms have positioned it as a pivotal player in regional and global trade dynamics. This article delves into the key aspects of Uzbekistan's foreign trade relations, highlighting its primary trade partners, major exports and imports, and the government's strategies to boost trade and economic growth.

Key words. currency liberalization, foreign economic and political relations, customs, tax incentives, exports, imports, business environment, diversification of trading partners, tourism, agriculture, public-private partnership, special economic zones, investment promotion agencies.

Foreign economic relations of Uzbekistan

Uzbekistan, as a sovereign state, is actively working to create an open economy. The basis for building an open-type economy is the country's broad participation in world economic relations and the international division of labor. Consistently implementing measures to deepen economic reforms and the formation of a socially oriented market economy, Uzbekistan proceeds from the indisputable fact that the market economy is a free economy, it is open, isolation and isolation are alien to it. In this regard, the future of our economy is seen in its integration with the world economy.

It is no coincidence that one of the important steps in ensuring the true sovereignty of the republic was the constitutional consolidation of Uzbekistan as an independent subject of international relations, determining foreign policy in its interests, having the right to join international organizations, collective security systems, and interstate entities.

The Republic of Uzbekistan has actively joined multilateral international mechanisms of economic cooperation, joined and began to pursue an active policy in reputable international financial and economic organizations such as the United Nations and its institutions, the World Bank, the International Monetary Fund, the International Finance Corporation, the Organization for

Economic Development Assistance, the International Labor Organization, the World Health Organization, and in other leading financial and economic organizations.

Many international organizations - the United Nations, the IMF, the World Bank, the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development, the Commission of the European Union and others have opened their regional offices in the republic and are actively cooperating with Uzbek partners.

A number of projects are being implemented, developed with the participation of the International Monetary Fund, the World Bank, the International Finance Corporation and contributing, in particular, to the development of small and medium-sized businesses in the republic and financial support for projects in priority areas of the economy.

Uzbekistan, together with the Central Asian States, became a member of the Economic Cooperation Organization, established by Turkey, Iran and Pakistan. Within the framework of this organization, the republic takes an active part in the development and implementation of projects for the joint construction of interstate transport communications, providing Uzbekistan with access to seaports, transnational transport networks, world markets for goods and capital.

It should be noted that Uzbekistan's cooperation with international organizations has been and will be based on a goal that combines both long-term and current priorities.

First, it is a strategic integration task - direct integration into international monetary, financial and trade mechanisms based on the creation of equal and national-interest conditions for the interaction of all economic entities of Uzbekistan with the outside world.

Secondly, it is a direct contribution to solving the current problems of the republic, support for ongoing reforms by obtaining financial, technical and advisory assistance from a number of these institutions based on existing international experience.

At the initial stage of the reforms, it was necessary to form a modern foreign economic complex of the republic from scratch, to create essentially a new mechanism for regulating foreign economic activity. During the three years of independence, the reform of foreign economic relations in Uzbekistan has made significant progress, primarily in organizational and legal aspects.

Practically all the necessary republican institutional structures have been re-established. As already noted, the Ministry of Foreign Economic Relations, the

National Bank for Foreign Economic Activity, and the Customs Service have been established. Relevant foreign economic units have been established and operate in the Cabinet of Ministers, ministries and departments, corporations, concerns, associations and local government bodies. The Republican International Trade Center is being created with the participation of foreign partners. We have opened trading houses in a number of countries around the world. Chambers of commerce and industry have been established on a bilateral basis between Uzbekistan and the United States, Great Britain, Germany and other countries interested in actively cooperating with the republic.

Since the beginning of the reform, the composition and structure of participants in foreign economic relations have changed. More than two thousand economic entities of the republic, including associations, concerns, small and private enterprises, have received the right to enter the foreign market.

In addition to foreign trade, other forms of foreign economic cooperation have noticeably intensified, and the number of enterprises with foreign investments established and operating in the republic is increasing.

During the first years of independence, the main legislative acts were adopted, presidential decrees and government decisions were issued, which laid the legal foundations for expanding foreign relations, liberalizing all foreign economic activity, stimulating the development of the export potential of the republic. These are, first of all, the laws "On Foreign Economic Activity", "On foreign investments and guarantees for the activities of foreign investors" and other legislative and regulatory acts that made it possible to form the basic framework conditions for the implementation of foreign economic relations, the conclusion and execution of international agreements in the field of foreign economic activity, to ensure the protection of the economic interests of the republic, legal entities and citizens of Uzbekistan for to establish legal guarantees for the activities of foreign investors in the territory of the republic.

The procedure for setting up joint ventures with foreign capital, registering participants in foreign economic activity and licensing exported products has been significantly simplified. All this has had a positive impact on the intensification of foreign economic activity and on improving the structure of exports and imports.

Foreign trade was carried out at the first stage of the reforms in two directions: with the CIS countries on the basis of concluded intergovernmental agreements and with foreign countries settlements in freely convertible currency. In

addition, the establishment of direct foreign economic cooperation ties was encouraged.

We give high priority to strengthening and developing multilateral ties and close cooperation with the Central Asian States. Indeed, the fraternal peoples of Central Asia are closely related to a common history, common cultural traditions, similar way of life and mentality, and many others. And the problems of today - political, economic, cultural, and environmental - in the Central Asian states largely coincide. The economies of these republics are highly integrated and have mutual influence.

One of the priorities of our foreign policy is the development of direct and multilateral relations with the countries forming the Commonwealth of Independent States.

With the participation of foreign partners, projects have been launched in the republic to create new joint ventures, such as Uz-Daewoo and UzDEUelectronics (Republic of Korea), Uzitalmotor JSC (Italy), Uzbekat (Great Britain), Khorezm APO (with Mercedes-Benz, Germany), textile enterprises, etc. Modernization of the republic's telephone networks has begun with the participation of German and South Korean companies.

Uzbekistan strives to take its rightful place in the world community. Uzbekistan is open to the world and we strive to ensure that the world is open to it.

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